

**DELINEATION OF THE INTERFACIAL CONFIGURATION IN A
SECTION OF MILLENNIUM CITY, KADUNA.**

BY

ALAO, JOSEPH OMEIZA

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DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICS,

FACULTY OF SCIENCE

KADUNA STATE UNIVERSITY, KADUNA

**IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENT FOR THE
AWARD OF A MASTER OF SCIENCE (M.Sc), PHYSICS DEGREE**

NOVEMBER, 2016

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the work in this thesis entitled “Delineation of the Interfacial Configuration in Some Parts of Millennium City, Kaduna, Using Geoelectrical Method”, has been performed by me in the Department of Physics, Kaduna State University, Kaduna, under the supervision of Dr. H. O. Aboh (Associate Professor of Applied Geophysics) and Dr. M.D. Dogara. All information provided in this work has been duly acknowledged in the text and the references provided. No part of this thesis has been previously presented for another Degree or Master Degree at any University.

Name

Signature

Date

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that Alao, Joseph Omeiza carried out the research work and produced this report under our supervision in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of a Master of Science (M.Sc) degree in Physics.

Dr. H.O. ABOH (Associate Professor of applied Geophysics) Major Project Supervisor	Date
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Dr. M.D. Dogara Minor Project Supervisor	Date
--	-------------

Dr. N.K Abdullahi Ag Head of Department	Date
---	-------------

External Examiner	Date
--------------------------	-------------

Prof. Bala Dongo Dean of Postgraduate School	Date
--	-------------

DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to God Almighty and my mother Mrs. Alao Hassanat.

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Effusive thanks go to Dr H.O. Aboh and Dr M.D. Dogara, my supervisors who have been working with me tirelessly in making relevant corrections all through this research. I wish to express my appreciation to Dr. N.K. Abdullahi of Department of Physics, Kaduna State University, Ephraim Wudda, Department of Minerals and Petroleum Resources Engineering, Kaduna Polytechnic and Prof. K.M. Lawal of Department of Physics, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, whose impact cannot be forgotten for their contributions in this work. My profound gratitude goes to all my lecturers for impacting knowledge into me especially M.S. Abubakar, Dr. S.G. Abdu, Dr P.M. Gyuk, and Prof Momoh. I give much credit to my family and my friends especially Kogi Kaza Akau and A. Ango for their support.

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GOD BLESS YOU ALL !!!.

ABSTRACT

The investigation of subsurface properties of a site for urban development is important in order to select the kind of structured foundation design for buildings and other amenities. A geoelectrical survey was carried out to determine the geotechnical characteristics as well as evaluate the groundwater potential of the study area. A total of thirty Vertical Electrical Soundings (VES) were carried out using Schlumberger electrode configuration with half current electrode spacing of maximum 100 m. The Interpreted data revealed that the study area is underlain by three to five layers. The top soils thickness and resistivity values vary from 0.3m – 9.0m and 100Ωm – 2100Ωm respectively. The thickness and resistivity of the weathered basements is between 11m – 42m and 35Ωm – 195Ωm respectively. The fresh basement layer which has resistivity values varies from 1000Ωm to 7500Ωm is of infinite depth and thickness. The competent zones where the basement rocks are highly resistive with a shallow depth have been recommended for construction work site such as high rise buildings and roads. Also, the areas where the basement rocks are deep are recommended for sewage and waste disposal site. Similarly, areas with relatively high thickness of the weathered layer and low resistivity values of the weathered and fracture zones have been successfully identified as potential aquifer zone targets for groundwater exploitation.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title Page	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Declaration	ii
Certification	iii
Dedication	iv
Acknowledgement	v
Abstract	vi
Table of Contents	vii
List of Tables	xi
List of Figures	xii
CHAPTER ONE	1
1.0 INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Project Background	2
1.2 Project Justification	3
1.3 The Study Area.....	4
1.3.1 Climate	5
1.3.2 Relief and Drainage	6
1.3.3 Soils and Vegetation	9
1.4 Geology and Hydrogeology of the Study Area.....	10

1.4.1	General Geology	10
1.4.2	Basement Geology Around the Study Area.....	11
1.4.3	Hydrogeology of the Basement Complex.....	13
1.5	Aim and Objectives of the Project	15
CHAPTER TWO		16
2.0	LITERATURE REVIEW.....	16
2.1	Causes of Structures Failure and unproductive Boreholes	16
2.2	Previous Geological Works in the Study Area	19
2.3	Previous Geotechnical works in the Study Area.....	20
CHAPTER THREE.....		22
3.0	METHODOLOGY	22
3.1	Introduction	22
3.2	Electrical Resistivity.....	23
3.2.1	Advantages of Electrical Resistivity	25
3.2.2	Limitations of Electrical Resistivity	25
3.3	Theoretical Background of Current Flow in the Ground.....	26
3.4	Electrode Configuration	27
3.5	Schlumberger Array	30
3.6	Field Work.....	33

3.7	The Choice of Method.....	33
3.8	Instrumentations and Materials	34
3.9	Data Acquisition.....	35
3.10	Electrical Configuration and Field Procedure.....	36
3.11	Precautions	37
CHAPTER FOUR.....		38
4.0	RESULT AND INTERPRETATIONS	38
4.1	Introduction	38
4.2	Data Processing	40
4.2.1	The Use of Crude Interpretation technique.....	40
4.2.2	The Use of Sounding Resistivity Curve Technique.....	41
4.2.3	The Use of Computer Software (surfer 11) for Contouring	41
4.3	Geoelectric and Geological Sections.....	42
4.3.1	Typical Resistivity Values from Previous Works.....	42
4.3.2	The VES Stations Interpreted Results.....	43
4.3.3	Typical Resistivity Values Adopted for this Work.....	48
4.4	RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	49
4.4.1	The Resistivity/Thickness of the Topsoil	49
4.4.2	The Resistivity/Thickness of Weathered Basement	53

4.4.3	The Basement Rock Resistivity/Depth to the Basement	57
4.4.4	Overburden.....	61
4.5	Evaluation of Competence	62
4.6	Evaluation of Aquifer Potential.....	63
CHAPTER FIVE.....		64
5.0	CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS.....	64
5.1	Conclusion.....	64
5.2	Recommendations	66
REFERENCES.....		67
LIST OF APPENDICES		Error! Bookmark not defined.

LIST OF TABLES

Table 4.1: Typical resistivity values compiled in different basement area in Kaduna State	42
Table 4.2: Typical resistivity of borehole lithology and interpretation	42
Table 4.3: Typical Resistivity from Romi, Chukun Local Government, Kaduna	43
Table 4.4: Typical Resistivity Values Adopted For this Work	48

LIST OF FIGURES

Fig. 1.1: Map of Nigeria Showing the Kaduna State and its Neighbouring States	5
Fig. 1.2: The Produced Orthographic Projection Map of the Study Area	7
Fig. 1.3: The Map of the Study Area showing the VES Stations and the Elevation	8
Fig. 1.4: Geological Map of Nigeria Showing the Study area.....	11
Fig. 1.5: Geological Map of Kaduna State Showing the Study Area.....	13
Fig. 3.1: The parameters used in defining resistivity.....	26
Fig. 3.2: Current flow from a single surface electrode.....	26
Fig. 3.3: The generalized form of the electrode configuration used in resistivity measurements.....	28
Fig. 3.4: Schlumberger array	32
Fig. 3.5: Scheme of the vertical electrical sounding (VES) device	35
Fig. 4.1: Typical resistivity curve obtained from the study area	44
Fig. 4.2: A typical geologic section obtained from well log in the study area ...	44
Fig. 4.3: Geoelectric/geologic section of profile one (1) across the study area .	45
Fig. 4.4: Geoelectric/geologic section of profile two (2) across the study area .	45
Fig. 4.5: Geologic/geologic section of profile three (3) across the study area ...	46
Fig. 4.6: Geoelectric/geologic section of profile four (4) across the study area	46
Fig. 4.7: Geoelectric/geologic section of profile five (5) across the study area...	47
Fig. 4.8: The Isopach Map of Topsoil	51

Fig. 4.9: The Iso-resistivity Map of Topsoil.....	51
Fig. 4.10: Topsoil thickness Orthographic projection map	52
Fig. 4.11: Topsoil resistivity Orthographic projection map	52
Fig. 4.12: The Isopach Map of Weathered Layer	55
Fig. 4.13: The Iso-rresistivity Map of Weathered Basement Layer	55
Fig. 4.14: The Orthographic projection map of Aquifer thickness.	56
Fig. 4.15: The Orthographic projection map of Aquifer resistivity.....	56
Fig. 4.16: The Iso-rresistivity Map of Basement Rock	59
Fig. 4.17: Depth to the Basement (Overburden Thickness) wMap	59
Fig. 4.18: The Orthographic projection map of the depth to the Basement	60
Fig. 4.19: Orthographic projection map of the Basement Resistivity Layer	60
Fig. 4.20: The Overburden Thickness orthographic map of the Study Area.....	61

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Large-scale urban sprawl and urbanization are common phenomenon in most developing countries. Building collapse and drinkable-water shortage are major problems confronting the people living in an urban settlement of the world. Urbanization has been accelerating at a tremendous rate. According to data collected by the United Nations 1990, 50 years ago less than 30 percent of the world population lived in cities (Lukuman, 2015). Now, more than 50 percent are living in urban settings which occupy only about one percent of the earth's surface. During the period from 1950 to 1995, the number of cities with population higher than one million increased from 85 to 325. According to the United Nations reports, by 2025, it is estimated that more than 60 percent of 8.3 billion people will be city dwellers (Lukuman, 2015). The alarming rate of structural failure such as roads, buildings, dam and bridges in Nigeria has become more intense.

Like other regions, Millennium City located in the capital City of Kaduna State is speculated to be a centre of attraction which may soon experience mass influx of people. In order to accommodate this expected population expansion, indiscriminate building of houses without proper geotechnical investigation, could lead to future disaster occurrence. The major problem and failure of engineers from the time past is the disregard of the fact that the design of any structure ought to proceed by a careful geophysical investigation of the site.

Thus, an adequate determination of geoelectrical and geological conditions at building sites is an essential component of proper City planning (Adebisi and Oloruntola, 2006). Adebisi and Oloruntola, (2006), observed that foundation failures are rarely due to facility structural design; they are usually related to failure of the load-bearing foundation with respect to the bed rock of the site. The geophysical studies provide the geotechnical information required in the engineering design in order to enhance the strength and the stability of the buildings or structures. The applications of such geophysical investigations are used for the determination of bedrock, structural mapping and evaluation of subsoil competence (Opara, 2006).

The aim of the present work is to apply the Schlumberger Vertical Electrical Soundings (VES) to delineate the interfacial configuration of the study area so as to ascertain its fitness for civil engineering and other related works as well as determine its groundwater potential.

1.1 Project Background

The failure statistics of structures such as buildings, tarred roads and bridges throughout the nation is increasing geometrically. Most of these failures were caused by swelling and shrinking of clays. Therefore, the knowledge of the probable cause of rampant failure of building foundations due to subsurface movements giving rise to cracks or structural differential settlements has been a great concern to geoscientists (Fadele, et al., 2012). Since structure foundation

ought to proceed by a careful geophysical investigation of the site. Thus, an adequate determination of geological conditions at building sites is an essential component of proper city planning in order to avoid any future foundation failures. On the other hand, all people irrespective of their development, economics and social condition are entitled to have access to drinking water in good quality and quantities (NWRI, 2011). Though, there is no evidence of any geophysical investigation that was carried out in the study area in the past but the previous research conducted in the neighbouring of the study area. These situations therefore make this type of investigation a *prima facie* for precise location of structure and productive boreholes site. While the government is largely responsible to protect life and properties of her citizen, this research will provide good information of subsurface properties underlain in the study area in order to adequately advise government.

1.2 Project Justification

The frequent collapse of building structures in Nigeria in the past few years has become very alarming and worrisome. In recent times the rates at which buildings collapse in Nigeria have been on the increase, killing people and destroying properties in the process. Adebisi and Oloruntola, (2006), are of the view that foundation failures are rarely due to facility structural design but usually related to failure of the load-bearing foundation beds. According to Loke, (1999), the involvement of geophysics in civil and environmental

engineering has become a promising approach in the last decade. Geophysical methods are implemented in a wide range of applications ranging from building ground investigations to the inspection of dams and dikes, which aids in the exploration of geological structures and the determination of the physical parameters of the rock and soil formations (Adebisi and Oloruntola, 2006). Like other places, Kaduna Millennium City is one of the centre of attraction in Kaduna State. Hence, there is need for good geophysical information of the subsurface nature of the area to avoid future disaster occurrence. This work can be helpful in providing geophysical survey data on the subsurface properties and the groundwater conditions of the study area to enable the engineers and other professions to understand the nature of the area for their application.

1.3 The Study Area

Kaduna State has approximately the total Landmass of 43,460 square kilometres with the total population of about 6,066,562, as reported by National population commission, (NPC), as at 2006. Kaduna State has boundaries with Niger State to the west, Federal Capital Territory (FCT) and Plateau State to the South and South-east, respectively, while Kano and Bauchi States have borders to the east of the study area (Fig 1.1). The study area, Millennium City, is bordered in the North by watercourse named Dan-Hono Stream and by Kubai Stream in the South, designated by watercourse. It is about 800 m away from proposed Kaduna State University Teaching Hospital site and about 3.6 km away from

Danbushiya Bridge. It lies on the geographical coordinate of latitude and longitude of $10^{\circ} 30.47' N$ to $10^{\circ} 31.08' N$, and $007^{\circ} 30.06' E$ to $007^{\circ} 30.33' E$ respectively. The location covers a total landmass of 200,000 square meters and with the average height of 607m (Kaduna Southeast sheet 123. 1:50,000) above the sea level.

Fig. 1.1: Map of Nigeria Showing the Kaduna State and its Neighbouring State

1.3.1 Climate

The climate of Kaduna is the tropical type, which has distinctive wet and dry seasons. Annual rainfall, ranging between 1000 to 1500mm, occurs between early April and early October. Maximum temperatures, on the other hand, vary between $38^{\circ}C$ in March/April and $24^{\circ}C$ in other months, but becomes far less in

peak rainy periods (July/August) and in harmattan months (November - February) (Titilayo, 2015). Kaduna State experiences a typical tropical continental climate with distinct seasonal regimes, oscillating between cool to hot dry and humid to wet (Mortimore, 1970). These two seasons reflect the influences of tropical continental and equatorial maritime air masses which sweep over the entire country. In Kaduna State, the seasonality is pronounced with the cool to hot dry season being longer than the rainy season. High storm intensities plus the nature of surface run off build up the good network of medium sized river systems. High evaporation during the dry season, however, sometimes creates water shortage problems (Mortimore, 1970).

1.3.2 Relief and Drainage

The study area is drained by both surface water and groundwater. The noticeable streams in the study area include Dan-Hono Stream and Kubai Stream, both drain into river Kaduna. The relief of the area is characterized by undulating plain, gentle slopes, and consists of peneplains with eroded flat tops (Fig. 1.4); often capped by layers of indurated laterites. Fig. 1.4 and 1.5 show the topography map and the contour map showing the elevation of the study area respectively. The southern boundary of the farm adjacent to the stream exhibits swampy conditions during rainy seasons, while the upper parts drain freely. The drainage pattern is dendritic while stream flow fluctuates seasonally.

Fig. 1.2: The Produced Orthographic Projection Map of the Study Area

Fig. 1.3: The Map of the Study Area showing the VES Stations and the Elevation

1.3.3 Soils and Vegetation

Kaduna vegetation type is Savannah. The vegetation of the area lies within a traditional zone, between the Guinean Savannah belt and the Sudan Savannah belt. The Guinean Savannah belt is characterised by a mixture of grassland and woodland while the Sudan Savannah belt is drier with a less humid climate, characterised by grass and thorn bush with baobab trees (Dogara, 1995). The Guinea Savannah type of vegetation in the area consists of broad-leaved savannah woodland which may attain heights of about 10 to 15 metres when fully developed, and may be dense enough to suppress the growth of grasses (Mortimore, 1970). Generally, the soils and vegetation are typical red brown to red yellow tropical ferruginous soils and savannah grassland with scattered trees and woody shrubs. The soils in the upland areas are rich in red clay and sand but poor in organic matter (Titilayo, 2015). However, soils within the "fadama" areas are richer in kaolinitic clay and organic matter, very heavy and poorly drained, characteristics of vertisols. Fringe forests ("Kurmi" in Hausa) in some localities, and especially in the southern LGAs of the state, are presently at the mercies of increasing demands for fuel wood in the fast growing towns and urban centres, (Mortimore, 1970). Both cash and food crops are grown in the study area which provide commodities for retailing in urban Kaduna. This include groundnuts, maize, guinea corn, millet, tomatoes, beans and a variety of vegetables. In some areas, fadama and dry season farming through irrigation canals are prominently under taken in the area.

1.4 Geology and Hydrogeology of the Study Area

1.4.1 General Geology

The general geology of Nigeria consists of two main lithological units. These are the Precambrian Crystalline Basement and Cretaceous-Tertiary sedimentary rocks (Oyawoye, 1970). The Regional distribution of rocks of the Nigerian Basement Complex is presented in Fig. 2.1. The Basement Complex rocks are of metamorphic igneous-volcanic origin. The main rock types units include: quartzite, meta-conglomerate, amphibolites, phyllites), Older Granites (granites) and Younger Granites (basalts, rhyolites, tuff), (Oyawoye, 1970).

Kaduna State is situated within the basement complex whose rocks consist mainly of the Migmatite-Gneiss Complex which consists of migmatites, biotites and granitic gneisses. The magnetite gneiss complex represents reactivated meta-sediment which is characterized by a variety of structures and textures (Oyawoye, 1970). Deep chemical weathering and fluvial erosion, influenced by the bioclimatic nature of the environment have developed the characteristics high undulating plains with subdued interfluves (Mortimore, 1970). The crystalline basement complex composes mainly of metamorphic rocks (Oyawoye, 1970).

Fig. 1.4: Geological Map of Nigeria Showing the Study area (Agbo, 2014)

1.4.2 Basement Geology Around the Study Area

Fig. 2.2 shows a detailed geological map of Kaduna State. The study area, Millennium City is underlain by precambrian rocks typical of the Nigeria basement complex which bears the imprints thermotectonic events dating from Achean to early paleozoic time (Oyawoye, 1970; Dogara, 1995). The typical rock types underlying the entire land area of Kaduna State consist of the Precambrian migmatite-gneiss complex, meta-sediments/ meta-volcanics (mostly schists, quartzites, amphibolites and banded Iron formations). Other include the Pan-African granitoids and calc-alkaline granites, and volcanics of

Jurassic age towards the south-eastern border of the States (Isaac, et al., 2010). The rocks in study area is capped by laterites, quartzites, sandstones and silty sand. The laterites are sometimes highly consolidated especially at the surface and weathered into lateritic nodules mixed with silty and sandy clays (Isaac, et al., 2010). Most of the areas underlain by the Basement Complex rocks in northern Nigeria consist of a thin discontinuous mantle of weathered rock overlying them. The average thickness of the weathered layer is about 15m, although depths of about 60m may be encountered. The unweathered bedrock is characterized by rapid grain-size variations from micro to pegmatitic regions but normal sizes are dominant (Isaac, e tal., 2010). The different basement rocks found around the undifferentiated basement complex as presented in Fig. 1.5 have been summarised as given by Dogara, (1995) to be;

- medium-coarse grained granite
- undifferentiated schist, including granite
- granite gneiss
- fine grained biotite and biotite-hornblends granite.
- Coarse porphyritic biotite and biotite-hornblends granite grained including quartz manorzite, and;
- Quartz diorite granodiorite.

Fig. 1.5: Geological Map of Kaduna State Showing the Study Area (Dogara, 1995)

1.4.3 Hydrogeology of the Basement Complex

The hydrogeology of an area is normally controlled by climatic and drainage factors of any region. This is because the geological formations underlying an area and their structures determine the type of aquifer that would be developed and the mean by which they would be recharged (Dogara, 1995). Like other places, the hydrogeology of Kaduna State to a large extent, is a function of the geologic setting. The surface water, which is directly governed by the

underlying geology, has its infiltration, evaporation, run-off and other flow components as major factors responsible for groundwater recharge/discharge and accumulation in the area (Dogara, 1995). The water-bearing units (aquifers) in basement rocks occur within the weathered residual overburden (the regolith) and the fractured bedrock (Isaac, et al., 2010). Viable aquifers wholly within the fractured bedrock are of rare occurrence because of the typically low storage of fracture systems, generally less than 1% (Isaac, et al., 2010). For a basement aquifer to produce effectively, the development of the bedrock component requires interactions with storage available in overlying or adjacent saturated regolith, or other suitable formations such as alluvium. However, areas with a thick regolith should be targeted for groundwater exploitation within the crystalline basement complex terrains. It has become a common groundwater exploration strategy in crystalline Basement terrains to site water supply boreholes where the regolith is thickest, with the expectation that the saturated thickness is greatest under such circumstances and the frequency of bedrock fissures also greatest (Oyawoye, 1970). The surface of the fresh basement is usually undulating. Hence the aquifer in most cases, is divided in isolated pockets. Thus the movement of the groundwater and drainage of aquifer is limited (Dogara, 1995). The major sources of aquifer recharge in the basement complex are rainfall, nearby rivers and streams.

1.5 Aim and Objectives of the Study

Aim:

This work is aimed at providing geotechnical information about the study area and the information on the aquifer potential of area in order to ensure proper engineering plans for situating structures.

Objectives:

The objectives of this current study are as follows:

- To determine the competent zone of the study area
- To delineate the various strata within the subsurface
- Providing information on the nature of the area's aquifer.
- To determine good knowledge of the basement geometry.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

In recent time, many geoelectrical investigations have been conducted to evaluate the competence of subsurface to select the kind of structures for site as well as hydrogeological work to determine the aquifer potential for groundwater development. Most of these works have provided a good background for this research work, thereby providing general information about the geology, hydrogeology and geoelectric of the subsurface layer around the study area that are used as guide for this research work. In the study area, there is no evidence of any published geophysical investigation that has been carried out there in the past. However, there are many other geophysical investigations that have been carried out around the study area.

2.1 Causes of Structures Failure and Unproductive Boreholes

Building collapse can be defined as the state of complete failure when the structure has literally given way and most members have either caved-in crumbled or buckled. A geotechnical survey is the first step in the construction or consolidation of a site (Loke, 1999). This includes information about soil consistency or competence and structure, groundwater level and recommendations for the technical project. The age-less interaction between man and his built environment has always had positive and negative impacts. Environmental disaster of varying origin from man-made to natural is one of the

most negative effects of the built environment on man. An assessment of the magnitude of these disasters and an evaluation of the existing capacities to prevent or prepare for them are necessary tools to provide future safe living for man in his built environment which has been great concern for several authors. Opara, (2006), noted that the sources of structure failure are not unconnected to the condition of subsurface geological features such as fractures, soil type, voids or cavities, shallow depth to the bedrock, near surface depth to the water table are among other common constraints to the building construction, especially to their foundation.

Fadele, et al., (2012), identified the growth of tree roots, organic deposits, sink holes, cavities or ground surface saturation among others as the major cause of buildings failure.

Adeniran, (2013), carried out a case study of building collapse as part of Environmental disasters management and identified poor soil, cavities and/or in-homogeneities in the foundation geo-materials as one of the major sources of hazards in civil engineering disciplines result essentially from undetected near-surface structures. The study further summarized the causes of structural failures in Nigeria from a series of building collapse investigations by the Nigerian Institute of Structural Engineers as follows:

- Non adherence to the approval regulation

- Absence of the involvement of a professional structural engineer in one or more of the stages of the project execution
- Incompetent and low quality workmanship
- Lack of soil investigation and improper interpretation of site conditions

Opara, (2006), identified poor soil stability as one of the factors that cause havoc in building construction due to the sensitiveness of soils to moisture loss or gain. Some clay soils for instance, can expand multiple times in volume if they get saturated with water and when there is loss of water in them, they shrink in volume. This expansion and contraction of clay soil cause cracks on building shortly after they are built.

According to Adefila, (1975), a survey of 69 boreholes drilled in the Basement complex rocks of Kaduna State, showed that 16 were unproductive, representing 30% failures, while the so-called successes were not encouraging due to low yield. This high rate of unproductive boreholes have been attributed to the fact that the boreholes were drilled at locations pre-determined by their owners, instead of on the basis of a good hydro-geological/geophysical investigation of the areas concerned. Most dug wells in the rural areas were located by 'common sense', or trial and error rather than by scientific methods due to restricted availability of equipment and operators.

2.2 Previous Geological Works in the Study Area

Aboh, (2009), worked on the assessment of the aquifers in some selected villages in Chikun local government area, Kaduna state, Nigeria. The Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) technique was used with the aim of determining the configuration of the aquifer within those areas mentioned. The study specifically identified the nature, extent and spatial distribution of the component of aquifer in the areas in order to provide information on the groundwater potential for improved exploitation of the water resource. The result suggests that the area is underlain by three to five layers. The geologic sections derived from the analyzed geo-electric section suggest that the alluvial deposits of sand, silt and sandy clay as well as the weathered and fractured basement rocks constitute the aquifer in the areas. The average thickness of the aquifer was found to be 25m. The result obtained also suggest that the resistivity values of the aquifer components range from 100 Ωm to 250 Ωm for the alluvial deposits to an average of 50 Ωm to 350 Ωm for the weathered/fractured basement formation.

Isaac, et al., (2010), studied the hydraulic characteristic such as depth to basement, screen length, pumping rate, specific capacity, regolith thickness and saturated thickness of some existing completed data from borehole around the areas using geophysical data based on electrical resistivity survey and the geological subsurface lithology obtained for the wells. The work showed that

the underlain aquifer has an average yield of 45.77 l/min (or 65.91m³/day) of water with higher yield occurring mainly in fractured zones. The study suggests that regolith and saturated thicknesses do not play significant role as much as hydraulic characteristics of weathered zone in aquifer productivity.

2.3 Previous Geotechnical Works in the Study Area

Fadele e tail., (2012), carried geophysical investigation for engineering around Ungwan Doka of Shika area which falls within the Basement Complex of North-Western Nigeria. The study was aimed at evaluating the competence of the near surface formation as foundation materials, and to unravel the subsurface profile which in turn determines if there would be any subsurface lithological variation(s) that might lead to structural failure. The resistivity values range from 26Ωm - 373Ωm; 77Ωm - 391Ωm; 473Ωm - 708Ωm; and 1161Ωm - 3600Ωm in the topsoil, weathered, fractured basement and fresh basement respectively. Layer thicknesses vary from 0.38m – 6.58m in the topsoil, 1.1m – 33.04m in the weathered layer, 5.86m – 34.1m in the fractured basement. Depth from the surface to bedrock/fresh basement generally varied between 2.65m and 37.75m. Based on the resistivity values, it is concluded that the subsurface material up to the depth of 25m is competent and has high load-bearing capacity. However, resistivity values less than 100Ωm at depths of 10m-15m indicates high porosity, high clayey sand content and high degree of saturation, which are indications of soil conditions requiring serious

consideration in the design of massive engineering structures. The presence of laterite beneath the clayey topsoil which hardly extends beyond 2.5m reduces the danger posed by clay formation to large buildings.

Abdullahi and Udensi, (2008), carried out Vertical Electrical Sounding Applied to Hydrogeology and Engineering Investigations at Kaduna Polytechnic Staff Quarters, Kaduna, Nigeria. The investigation was aimed to delineate the best site for locating borehole and structures. In the work, total of Sixty-six (66) VES was established, and a maximum of four geologic units was defined. The upmost layer (laterite, river sand, and gravel) followed by clayey sand, weathered basement and fractured/fresh basement. The nature of the overburden and the topography of the bed rock were determined. Thus, the study identified:

- Weathered/fractured basement transition zone as the main aquifer unit.
- High resistivity basement area as competent zone for siting construction works such as buildings, roads and bridges and high depth to the basement for waste disposal and sewage
- Fractured and severe weathered zones for good aquifer but incompetence.

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

Electrical resistivity is a geophysical method in which an electrical current is injected into the ground through steel electrodes in an attempt to measure the electrical properties of the subsurface (Loke, 1999). Its technique is based on the response of the subsurface material to the flow of electric current in subsurface (Keller, 1979). Most soils and non-ore bearing rocks are electrically resistive, (i.e. insulators). Soil moisture and ground water are often electrically conductive due to contained dissolved minerals (John, 2003). Therefore, the resistivity measured in the ground is predominantly controlled by the amount of moisture and water within the soil and rock (a function of the porosity and permeability), and the concentration of dissolved solids (salts) in that water (Telford, et al., 1990). The basic method requires at least 4 steel electrodes be driven into the ground. An electrical current is then applied to the outer electrodes by a battery or generator. A voltage is measured between the two (2) inner electrodes using a simple voltmeter. Through Ohm's Law ($V = IR$) and by knowing the input current, the measured voltage and the geometry of the electrode array, a value known as resistance can be calculated (Kearey, et al.,

2002). Resistivity, measured in Ohm-meters, is resistance times area geometry factor. Because the actual current flow is highly influenced by conductive layers, the value measured is known as the “apparent resistivity” (Loke, 1999).

3.2 Electrical Resistivity

Electrical resistivity is one of the common methods used in geophysical investigation of subsurface. The electrical resistivity measurements are normally made by injecting current into the ground through two current electrodes (A and B in Fig 3.3), and measuring the resulting voltage difference at two potential electrodes (C and D). From the current (I) and voltage (V) values, an apparent resistivity (ρ) value is calculated as; $\rho = \frac{kV}{I}$; where k is the geometric factor which depends on the arrangement of the four electrodes. Resistivity meters normally give a resistance value, $R = \frac{V}{I}$; so in practice the apparent resistivity value is calculated by $\rho = kR$.

The calculated resistivity value is not the true resistivity of the subsurface, but an “apparent” value which is the resistivity of a homogeneous ground which will give the same resistance value for the same electrode arrangement. The relationship between the “apparent” resistivity and the “true” resistivity is a complex relationship (Loke, 1999). To determine the true subsurface resistivity, an inversion of the measured apparent resistivity values using a computer program must be carried out. Resistivity of subsurface material is generally a function of porosity, water saturation, connectivity of pore space (permeability),

and ionic content of the pore fluid and clay mineralization (Loke, 1999). Vertical electrical sounding (also known as electrical drilling' or 'expanding probe) is one of the surveying techniques used in electrical prospecting for groundwater. It measures the vertical variation of resistivity with depth. This is achieved based on two assumptions. The subsurface is assumed to be homogenous and isotropic (Telford, et al., 1990; Loke, 1999). The exploration of geological structures and the determination of the physical parameters of the rock formations is vital in survey techniques. Resistivity, measured in Ohm-meters, is resistance times area divided by distance. Because the actual current flow is highly influenced by conductive layers, the value measured is known as the "apparent resistivity". In its simplest terms, it represents an average value encompassing all of the different materials within the volume (half-space) of materials being measured. Most modern resistivity meters calculate apparent resistivity once the geometric parameters are input. Applications of these investigations in Engineering and Environmental Sites include Stratigraphic and Ground Water Mapping Surveys.

For these applications, the basic method used is to set up electrical arrays at several locations on a site, and measure changes in resistivity as a function of depth. This is accomplished by increasing the electrode spacing while leaving the centre of the array at the same location. Generally, the "a" spacing starts at one foot or meter, and is doubled for each successive measurement. A very general rule of thumb is that the depth of the investigation is equal to about half

to one-third the “a” spacing. This method is known as the “vertical electrical sounding” and would be the method used to determine the depth of a clay layer, ground water, or bedrock. Once the depth to a feature of interest is determined using the sounding method, the feature may be tracked by moving the array across a Site, keeping the “a” spacing the same. This method of exploration is called “profiling” (Loke, 1999).

3.2.1 Advantages of Electrical Resistivity

- Soundings can be used to determine the depth and thickness of subsurface layers, depth to the water table, and bedrock.
- Profiling can be used to detect and locate contaminant plumes.
- Resistivity values can be used to estimate geological formations (Loke, 1999).

3.2.2 Limitations of Electrical Resistivity

- Like all geophysical methods resistivity data are ambiguous, meaning that many different “models” can produce the same data. To narrow down the number of possible models, other geological information is needed (borehole and/or monitoring well data).
- Electrical resistivity is slow because electrodes must be driven into the ground between measurements.
- Data are influenced by near surface conductive layers. The current will always travel most easily along highly conductive layers (Loke, 1999). If the surface is highly conductive it may not be possible to collect data below the top layer.

3.3 Theoretical Background of Current Flow in the Ground

The resistivity of a material is defined as the resistance in ohms between the opposite faces of a unit cube of the material (Kearey, et al., 2002). For a conducting cylinder of resistance (δR), length (δL) and cross-sectional area (δA) (Fig. 3.1) the resistivity ρ is given by;

$$\rho = \frac{\delta R \delta A}{\delta L} \text{-----3.1}$$

Fig. 3.1: The parameters used in defining resistivity

In an element of homogeneous material as shown in Fig. 3.1, current I is passed through the cylinder causing a potential drop ($-\delta V$) between the ends of the element. Ohm's law relates the current, potential difference and resistance such that $-\delta V = \delta R I$, and from equation (3.1) $\delta R = \frac{\delta V}{I}$. Substituting

Fig. 3.2: Current flow from a single surface electrode.

$$\frac{\delta V}{\delta L} = -\frac{\rho I}{\delta A} \text{-----} 3.2$$

$\frac{\delta V}{\delta L}$ represents the potential gradient through the element in voltm^{-1} and J the current density in Am^{-2} . In general, the current density in any direction within a material is given by the negative partial derivative of the potential in that direction divided by the resistivity. Now consider a single current electrode on the surface of a medium of uniform resistivity ρ (Fig. 3.2). The circuit is completed by a current sink at a large distance from the electrode. Current flows radially away from the electrode so that the current distribution is uniform over hemispherical shells centred on the source. At a distance (r) from the electrode the shell has a surface area of $2\pi r^2$, so the current density J is given by

$$J = \frac{I}{2\pi r^2} \text{-----} 3.3$$

So, from equation (3.2), the potential gradient associated with this current density is

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial r} = -\frac{\rho I}{2\pi r^2} = -\rho J \text{-----} 3.4$$

The potential (V_r) at distance r is then obtained by integration;

$$V_r = \int \partial V = -\int \frac{\rho I \partial r}{2\pi r^2} = \frac{\rho I}{2\pi r} \text{-----} 3.5$$

3.4 Electrode Configuration

Many configurations of electrodes have been designed, although several are occasionally employed in specialized surveys, only two are in common use (John, 2003). That is Wenner and Schlumberger array. In Vertical electrical

sounding, there are different arrays that can be used to carry out electrical survey for groundwater and subsurface survey such as:

- Gradient array
- Square array
- Pole-dipole array
- Pole-pole array
- Dipole-dipole array
- Wenner array
- Schlumberger array

The general formula for the resistivity measured by a four electrode method is simpler for some special geometry of the current and potential electrodes (Kearey, e tal., 2002).

Fig. 3.3: The generalized form of the electrode configuration used in resistivity measurements.

Now consider Fig 3.3, where the current sink is a finite distance from the source. The potential (V_C) at an internal electrode C is the sum of the potential contributions (V_A) and (V_B) from the current source at A, and the sink at B.

$$V_C = V_A + V_B \text{-----} 3.6$$

From (3.5)

$$V_C = \frac{\rho I}{2\pi} \left[\frac{1}{r_A} - \frac{1}{r_B} \right] \text{-----} 3.7$$

Similarly,

$$V_D = \frac{\rho I}{2\pi} \left[\frac{1}{R_A} - \frac{1}{R_B} \right] \text{-----} 3.8$$

Absolute potentials are difficult to monitor, so the potential difference (ΔV) between electrodes C and D is measured

$$\Delta V = V_C - V_D = \frac{\rho I}{2\pi} \left[\left(\frac{1}{r_A} - \frac{1}{r_B} \right) - \left(\frac{1}{R_A} - \frac{1}{R_B} \right) \right] \text{-----} 3.9$$

Thus

$$\rho_a = \frac{2\pi\Delta V}{I \left[\left(\frac{1}{r_A} - \frac{1}{r_B} \right) - \left(\frac{1}{R_A} - \frac{1}{R_B} \right) \right]} \text{-----} 3.10$$

Hence, the general equation becomes;

$$\rho_a = 2\pi \frac{V}{I} \left[\left(\frac{1}{r_{AC}} - \frac{1}{r_{CB}} \right) - \left(\frac{1}{r_{AD}} - \frac{1}{r_{BD}} \right) \right]^{-1} \text{-----} 3.11$$

(Kearey, e tal., 2002)

The term ρ_a in equation (3.11) is called Apparent Resistivity. Before discussing the various electrode spreads, it is necessary to consider what is actually measured by an array of current and potential electrodes. We can rearrange equation (3.11) to obtain any configuration where the parameter ρ_a has to do with the electrode geometry (Kearey, et al., 2002). By measuring V and I and knowing the electrode configuration, we obtain a resistivity (ρ_a). In a homogeneous isotropic ground this resistivity will be constant for any current

and electrode arrangement. If the ground is inhomogeneous, the electrode spacing is varied, or the spacing remains fixed while the whole array is moved, then the ratio will, in general, change (Telford, et al., 1990). The geometrical factor (K) depends on the arrangement of the four electrodes. This factor can be obtained using the Laplace equation in polar coordinates to derive the electrical potential functions around the source (A and B) and measuring (C and D) electrodes (Keller and Frischknecht, 1966). The geometric factor K can be defined for four-electrode array of ACDB configuration as

$$K = \frac{2\pi}{\left(\frac{1}{r_{AC}} - \frac{1}{r_{BC}}\right) - \left(\frac{1}{r_{AD}} - \frac{1}{r_{BD}}\right)} \text{-----} 3.12$$

where (r_{AC}), (r_{BC}), (r_{AD}), and (r_{BD}) are the distances in metres between the respective electrodes. For central-symmetric array, when (r_{AC}) = (r_{BD}) and (r_{BC}) = (r_{AD}), Eq. (3.12) can be simplified to

$$K = \pi \frac{[r_{AC}][r_{AD}]}{[r_{CD}]} \text{-----} 3.13$$

(Kearey, et al., 2002)

3.5 Schlumberger Array

The Schlumberger array consists of four collinear electrodes. The outer two electrodes (AB) are current (source) electrodes and the inner two electrodes (CD) are the potential (receiver) electrodes. The potential electrodes are installed at the centre of the electrode array with a small separation, typically

less than one fifth of the spacing between the current electrodes. The current electrodes are increased to a greater separation during the survey while the potential electrodes at the centre point of the electrode array remains fixed, but the spacing between the electrodes is increased to obtain more information about the deeper sections of the subsurface. In the Schlumberger configuration (Fig. 3.4), the current and potential pairs of electrodes often also have a common mid-point, but the distances between adjacent electrodes differ. Let the separations of the current and potential electrodes be L and a, respectively.

Then:

$$r_{AC} = r_{BD} = (L - a)/2 \text{ -----} 3.14$$

$$r_{CB} = r_{AD} = (L + a)/2 \text{ -----} 3.15$$

Substituting (3.14) and (3.15) into the general formula (3.11), we get (3.16)

$$\rho_a = 2\pi \frac{V}{I} \left[\left(\frac{2}{L-a} - \frac{2}{L+a} \right) - \left(\frac{2}{L+a} - \frac{2}{L-a} \right) \right]^{-1} \text{ -----} 3.16$$

$$\rho_a = 2\pi \frac{V}{I} \left[\left(\frac{4a}{L^2-a^2} \right) - \left(-\frac{4a}{L^2-a^2} \right) \right]^{-1} \text{ -----} 3.17$$

$$\rho_a = 2\pi \frac{V}{I} \left[\left(\frac{8a}{L^2-a^2} \right) \right]^{-1} \text{ -----} 3.18$$

$$\rho_a = 2\pi \frac{V}{I} \left[\frac{L^2-a^2}{8a} \right] \text{ -----} 3.19$$

$$\rho_a = \frac{\pi V}{4I} \left[\frac{L^2-a^2}{a} \right] \text{ -----} 3.20$$

Fig. 3.4: Schlumberger array

In this configuration the separation of the current electrodes is kept much larger than that of the potential electrodes ($L \gg a$).

There are other arrays such as multi-electrode array, offset wenner array, and focuses array which are also useful in their respective interpretation. The most common used configurations are the Wenner and Schlumberger arrangements. In each configuration the four electrodes are collinear but their geometries and spacing are different.

Using the Schlumberger configuration, potential electrode CD is placed in between the current electrodes AB with a central reference point established. As a rule of thumb, the distance $AB/2$ is always greater or equal to five times the distance $CD/2$. The current electrodes AB are moved outward symmetrically at each successive reading for deeper current penetration and thus deeper probing. The distance between the CD electrodes is increased when the current electrode AB are relatively far apart while maintaining CD being much less than AB. This is done in order to have measurable potentials and to prevent the voltage from dropping below the reading accuracy of the voltmeter (Kearey, et al., 2002).

3.6 Field Work

The field work was carried out between 20th January to 27th February, 2016. This season of the year was chosen to avoid unnecessary increment in the level of ground conductivity and any possible disturbance by rain. Schlumberger array of electrical resistivity imaging was used along five (5) profiles with six (6) VES on each profile making a total of thirty (30) VES points. A direction of NW-SE azimuth was employed in the orientation of all the profiles. The direction was employed to ensure a desirable field space for the work.

3.7 The Choice of Method

The choice of array and its dimension largely depend upon the target; its size, depth and resistivity contrast with its surroundings. For this present study, Schlumberger configuration was adopted for the following reasons:

1. The Schlumberger array provides for high signal to noise ratio.
2. Schlumberger requires fewer electrodes to be moved for each sounding.
3. It has excellent vertical resolution and good depth sensitivity (Loke, 1999)
4. The manpower and time required for making Schlumberger sounding are less compared to that required for other arrays such as Wenner profiling.
5. It permits the acquisition of data within a very short time.
6. The effect of near-surface, lateral in-homogeneities affect Schlumberger measurements less than it affects the Wenner measurements.

7. The interpretation techniques are more fully developed and more diversified for Schlumberger sounding curves than Wenner sounding curves.

3.8 Instrumentations and Materials

In this survey, the instruments used for data collection are; Omega resistivity Terrameter and its components, magnetic compass, field hammer, cutlass, ranging poles, pegs, electrodes, cables and reels, measuring tape, Global Positioning System (GPS), and other accessories.

Fig. 3.6 shows the Scheme of the vertical electrical sounding (VES) device and it penetrating current where [1] Omega resistivity Terrameter; [2] Potential probes; [3] Current probes; [4, 5 and 6] Different subsurface; [7] Current flow; [AB] Current electrode spacing; [CD] Potential electrodes spacing. The vertical electrical sounding and electrical profiling methods used are based on the four-electrode principle as shown in Fig. 3.3. The electrical current (I) is applied to A and B electrodes and the potential (ΔV) is measured between C and D electrodes. The depth of sounding increases with the distance between A and B electrodes. The K factors for the combinations are calculated with Eq. [3.13] and used to obtain electrical resistivity from measured electrical potential and current using Eq. [3.20]. The result of VES measurements with central-symmetric arrays is apparent (bulk) electrical resistivity as a function of half of the distance between the current electrodes, i.e. $ER = f(AB/2)$. The relationship between ER and $AB/2$ can be converted into a relationship between electrical resistivity and actual soil depth through a computer interpretation (Kearey, et al., 2002).

Fig. 3.5: Scheme of the vertical electrical sounding (VES) device

3.9 Data Acquisition

An Omega Resistivity Terrameter and its accessories, Global Positioning System (GPS) were used to obtain all the field data. A total of thirty (30) vertical electrical sounding (VES) points were established at different locations within the study area with maximum spread ($AB/2$) of 100 meters and $MN/2$ from 0.3 to 5 m with a view to determining the subsurface layering, overburden thickness, thickness of the aquiferous layer and the degree of fracturing of the bedrock. The observed field data were converted to apparent resistivity values by multiplying with the Schlumberger geometric factor. The sounding curve for

each point was obtained by plotting the apparent resistivity on the ordinate against half current-electrode spacing on a logarithmic transparent paper.

3.10 Electrical Configuration and Field Procedure

During the field work, the following procedures were followed:

1. Four range poles were used to get a straight line
2. A 100 meters tape rule was laid along the straight line
3. Electrodes were used to mark both the current and potential spacing (See table 3.1).
4. The current and potential wheel cables were connected to the Terrameter
5. Crocodile clips were used to connect the wheel cables to the electrodes
6. The readings were taken from the Terrameter for each successful mark for both current and electrode.
7. The same procedure was followed for all other VES points.

3.11 Precautions

According to Dogara, (1995), the computer program use in the interpretation of this work is very versatile but extra care can be taken in using it as it can produce models which are totally implausible geologically. During the field data acquisition, the following precautions were observed.

1. The tight connection was carefully made.
2. Care was taken to avoid damage of insulated current cables that could lead to current leakage into the ground.
3. Care was taken to ensure that the electrodes penetrated well into the ground to ensure good contact.
4. Caution was taken while laying the cables for effective current flow.
5. The terrameter was off after each successive reading and on when taking next reading. This was done to prevent the readings from interfering.
6. Readings were not taken under sources such as high tension, metallic pipe lines in order not to increase or interfere with the readings.
7. Distance $AB/2$ being greater or equal to five times the distance $CD/2$ was maintained throughout the survey.
8. Care was taken to ensure linearity while laying the electrodes.
9. The terrameter was kept under shade to maintain good temperature and to avoid damage from direct rays from the sun.

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 RESULT AND INTERPRETATIONS

4.1 Introduction

Schlumberger sounding was carried out under the constraint CD is small compared to $AB/2$. A common guideline that CD must not exceed 20% $AB/2$ was followed. The fields proceed by expanding $AB/2$ while CD remains constant. This process yields a rapidly decreasing potential difference across CD, which ultimately exceeds the measuring capabilities of the instrument (El-Arabi, 2008). At this point new value for CD is established, typically 3-4 times larger than the preceding values, and the survey continues until the last two or three $AB/2$ is duplicated with the new CD value. To illustrate, we started the survey with $CD = 0.3$ meter. $AB/2$ values are taken as $AB/2 = 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 3.0, 4.5, 7.0$. At 7.0, we suppose that the instrument sensitivity has declined such that a larger value of CD is required. Then, we increased it to $CD = 1.0$ and repeat the last one $AB/2$ value, and continue with $AB/2 = 10.0, 15.0, 20.0, 30.0, 45.0$. At $AB/2 = 45.0$, we changed CD to 5.0, and also repeat the last one $AB/2$ value, and continue with $AB/2 = 70.0$ and 100.0. The process continues this way until the survey is completed. The change in CD value during the process of the sounding introduces a problem for interpretation, but also an unexpected benefit. The problem arises because the apparent resistivity values turn out to differ slightly for the same $AB/2$ value when CD is changed (El-Arabi, 2008).

The effect is shown in fig.4.1. For interpretation, we converted the segmented curve to a single smooth curve. Fig.4.2, shows the converted curve.

Fig. 4.1: Unconverted Segmented Curve to a Single Smooth Curve Schlumberger Electrical Sounding

Fig. 4.2: Converted Segmented Curve to a Single Smooth Curve Schlumberger Electrical Sounding

4.2 Data Processing

Vertical sounding field curves can be interpreted qualitatively using simple curve shapes, semi-quantitatively with graphical model curves, or quantitatively with computer modelling (Telford, et al., 1990). In order to investigate the subsurface structural trends in the study area, and to reveal the lithological sequence of the subsurface formation, the field data was processed using three different computer program and interpretation techniques were used to interpret the data obtained.

4.2.1 The Use of Crude Interpretation technique

The first stage in any interpretation of apparent resistivity sounding curves is to note the curve shape (Telford et al., 1990). Before applying a more complicated methods of interpretation, it is useful to consider a few rough ideas. Fig. 4.1 shows a pair of resistivity curves for three layers. This can be classified simply for three electrical layers into one of four basic curve shapes which can be combined to describe more complex field curves that may have several more layers. This curve allows us to determine the model parameters like initial model layers and the curve types (such as A, H, K, Q, KH, HA-type) of the study area (Telford et al., 1990). The values of apparent resistivity obtained are plotted on a graph (field curve), the x- and y-axes of which represent the logarithmic values of the current electrode half-separation ($AB/2$) and the

apparent resistivity (ρ_a), respectively to estimate the depth and resistivities of the bed rocks using excel 2007, (Fig. 4.1).

4.2.2 The Use of Sounding Resistivity Curve Technique

The form of the curves obtained by sounding is a function of the resistivities and thicknesses of the layers as well as of the electrode configuration. It is the most rigorous technique the interpreter normally spends much time trying to obtain a perfect fit between computer generated and field curves (El-Arabi, 2008). This involves the use of computer Iteration Software (*Res1D*). It is an automatic computer programme that determines the resistivity model for the subsurface data obtained from electrical survey. The typical resistivity sounding curves obtained from the area is done by feeding in the data obtained into Res1D (version 1.00.07 Beta) software with initial model parameters which will give us an inversion results (See Fig. 4.3). The sounding interpreted data is used to obtain geoelectric and geologic section presented in section 4.4.

4.2.3 The Use of Computer Software (surfer 11) for Contouring

This section involves the production of maps. An automatic computer programme was used for contouring to reveal the variation in resistivity, depth to the basement (overburden thickness) and thickness underlain layer by the study area. The latitude and longitude coordinate is presented as abscissa and ordinate respectively) and the inversion values from Res1D as “Z” axis which

processed by Computer Software (Surfer 11) to produce the corresponding (Fig. 4.8 – 4.20).

4.3 Geoelectric and Geological Sections

The geoelectric section describes the electrical properties the formation of a sequence of layered rocks (El-Arabi, 2008).

4.3.1 Typical Resistivity Values from Previous Works

Tables 4.1-4.3 reveal the typical resistivity values compiled in different basement area from different author in Kaduna State.

Table 4.1: Typical resistivity values compiled in different basement area in Kaduna State (Agbo , 2014: Aboh, 2009: Abdullahi and Udensi, 2008)

Soil and Rock Types	Resistivity (Ωm)
Clay-fresh water	30 – 70
Dry clay	40 – 100
Weathered basement	50 – 100
Laterite	200 – 400
Slightly weathered basement	200 – 500
Dry sand	500 – 1000
Fresh crystalline basement rock	>1000

Table 4.2: Typical resistivity of borehole lithology and interpretation modified from Aboh, (2001).

BOREHOLE	
Laterite top soil, clayey, brownish (700-900 ohm-m)	15m
Sand, fine, silty, slightly compacted, and light brownish (250 – 400 ohm-m)	
Cuttings of fractured basement rocks (300 – 400 ohm-m)	30m
Fresh basement (3000-4000 ohm-m)	38m

Table 4.3: Typical Resistivity from Romi, Chukun Local Government, Kaduna (Dogara, 1995).

Soil and Rock Types	Resistivity (Ωm)
Fadama loam	30 – 90
Sandy clay and sandy silt	91 – 200
Weathered laterite	201 – 850
Fresh laterite	850 – 3500
Weathered basement	20 – 160
Fractured basement	500 – 1000
Fresh basement	>1000

4.3.2 The VES Stations Interpreted Results

Fig. 4.4 shows the geologic section obtained from well log in the study area, (Ephraim Wudda, 2015) while Fig. 4.5 – 4.9 show the composite geoelectric and geologic section derived for the VES stations established along all the five profiles. The resulting curves and their final model parameters after quantitative interpretation are presented in Fig. 4.3 and Table 4.4. The final model geoelectric parameters across the sections of the study area were used for the preparation of the geoelectric ad geologic section (Fig. 4.4-4.9). The geoelectric sections show the average variations of resistivity and thickness values of layers within the depth penetrated in the study area at the indicated sections. Generally, the sections revealed three to five subsurface layers: topsoil/laterite/indurated laterite/quartzite veins, clay/silty/sand, laterite, weathered/fractured layer and the fresh basement as shown in Fig. 4.4 – 4.9.

Fig. 4.1: Typical resistivity curve obtained from the study area

Fig. 4.2: A typical geologic section obtained from well log in the study area, (Ephraim Wudda, Department of Minerals and Petroleum Resources Engineering, Kaduna Polytechnic)

Fig. 4.3: Geoelectric/geologic section of profile one (1) across the study area

Fig. 4.4: Geoelectric/geologic section of profile two (2) across the study area

Fig. 4.5: Geologic/geologic section of profile three (3) across the study area

Fig. 4.6: Geolectric/geologic section of profile four (4) across the study area

Fig. 4.7: Geoelectric/geologic section of profile five (5) across the study area

Table4: 1 VES stations interpreted results

VES points	Resistivity (Ωm) $\rho_1/\rho_2/\rho_3\text{---}\rho_n$	Thickness (m) $h_1/h_2/h_3 \text{ - } /h_n$	Curves type
1	977.7/641.3/77.3/1017.1	3.8/9.0/24.0	QH
2	1100.8/526.2/150.3/1052.4	5.1/10.6/32.7	QH
3	125.2/876.6/35.9/1865.2	4.7/4.9/16.2	KH
4	614.1/231.7/120.4/555.7/1607.5	1.3/20.0/15.4/14.7	QHA
5	263.6/134.0/1110.4	4.7/24.1	H
6	407.6/121.5/1931.2	1.4/26.0	H
7	670.4/3490.4/121.7/1711.1	5.2/6.2/23.3	KH
8	713.0/897.4/192.8/1051.1	1.5/16/32.5	KH
9	1995.6/873.2/106.7/1573.5	1.3/8.1/30.5	QH
10	293.2/459.9/67.7/7337.0	0.9/4.5/12.6	KH
11	859.5/284.8/655.5/3728.12	0.4/1.0/2.3/11.9	HKH
12	450.8/142.3/1508.9	1.0/34.3	H
13	331.8/37.2/1564.0/36.0/1949.5	0.7/0.7/2.5/14.7	HKH
14	1613.9/1237.3//59.8/1944.7	11.1/14.1	QH
15	432.3/1128.8/101.0/1502.0	3.9/7.7/18.5	KH
16	229.7/430.9/102.9/1136.4	1.1/3.0/20.2	KH
17	413.0/141.3/589.2/41.8/1749.4	0.6/1.2/3.1/11.6	HKH
18	304.9/96.9/4808.9	1.2/27.5	H
19	724.5/953.3/124.6/1678.8	0.9/6.3/33.3	KH
20	474.6/153.1/2737.2	9.7/37.8	H
21	783.3/463.3/63.2/1053.8	1.1/9.7/18.6	QH
22	376.3/171.3/404.6/83.4/1349.0	0.5/5.0/8.2/22.1	HKH
23	413.1/39.2/674.4/51.8/1355.3	1.0/1.0/2.6/11.2	HKH
24	305.1/78.1/3226.7	2.1/20.3	H
25	416.7/181.8/2881.3	1.5/39.5	H
26	2072./616.05/70.9/2226.6	1.0/4.8/25.8	QH
27	1592.2/495.4/136.6/1713.8	0.8/4.7/40.5	QH
28	261.8/491.1/87.7/1478.1	0.3/4.9/21.5	KH
29	867.6/258.4/846.5/155.2/1069.7	0.8/4.2/7.5/20.8	HKH
30	279.4/58.3/6781.1	1.3/16.9	H

4.3.3 Typical Resistivity Values Adopted for this Work

This section was constructed using the results of the research work after Dogara, (1995) and Aboh, (2009)

Table 4.4: Typical Resistivity Values Adopted For this Work

Soil and Rock Types	Resistivity range
Top layer (clay/indurated laterite/quartzite veins)	125-2100 Ωm
Silt/Sandy/clay, Fadama loam	37 – 250 Ωm
Weathered/fresh Laterite	250-3500 Ωm
Weathered Basement	35-195 Ωm
Fractured Basement	300-1000 Ωm
Fresh basement	>1000 Ωm

4.4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.4.1 The Resistivity/Thickness of the Topsoil

Fig. 4.8 and 4.9 show the isopach map and iso-resistivity of the topsoil zone respectively. The map shows that the topsoil is highly variable in thickness and resistivity; with values $0.3 - 10m$ and $125 \Omega m - 2100 \Omega m$ respectively, which could be used to compare the surface feature such as stream and laterite/indurated laterite at the top layer. Fig. 4.9 shows that the topsoil is highly resistivity at the VES stations (depicted by red colour) with high resistivity values ($1000 \Omega m - 2100 \Omega m$); the high resistivity in this region may be probably the presence of indurated laterite/quartzite veins at the top layer. According to Bayowa and Olayiwola, (2015), any region with resistivity values $300 \Omega m$ and above may be considered good enough for massive structures. Considering the nature of the top layer (presence of indurated laterites and quartzite veins), the observed high resistivity ($1000 - 2100 \Omega m$) around southwest and north-central part depicted by red colour could be considered high competent region and is good enough for massive construction works. The area with relatively high resistivity ($300 \Omega m - 1000 \Omega m$) was observed to dominate most part of the area; these regions may be considered for Engineering and construction purposes depending on the underlain subsurface properties (Bayowa & Olayiwola, 2015: Abdullahi and Udensi, 2008). The observed relatively low resistivity ($< 300 \Omega m$), in the Northeast and Southeast parts may not be unconnected with the nature of the topsoil and the adjacent

stream. This could be considered for small civil engineering as well. Fig. 4.8 reveals the variation of the top lay in thickness. Fadele, et al., (2012), observed that the thickness of top soil may be considered as one of the parameters used to describe the site competence. Base on this information; the topsoil materials (consist of indurated laterites, quartzite veins and their corresponding relatively high resistivity values), the regions with topsoil thickness values of .15m – 5.0m and 5.1 – 10m as depicted by red and green colours respectively may be considered good for massive engineering structures. The regions of superficial cover that may post danger to engineering structures should be evacuated before siting any engineering structures.

On the other hand, Fig. 4.10 and 4.11 show the corresponding orthographic projection map of thickness and resistive of the top layer respectively.

Fig. 4.8: The Isopach Map of Topsoil

Fig. 4.9: The Iso-resistivity Map of Topsoil

Fig. 4.10: Topsoil thickness Orthographic projection map

Fig. 4.11: Topsoil resistivity Orthographic projection map

4.4.2 The Resistivity/Thickness of Weathered Basement

Fig. 4.12 and 4.13 show the isopach map and iso-resistivity of the weathered basement respectively with average resistivity and thickness values of $99\Omega\text{m}$ and 23m respectively which closely agreed with (Aboh, 2009). The thickest part of the aquifer was found to be region around VES points $L_{4/2}$, $L_{5/1}$, and $L_{5/3}$ with thickness of 37.8m, 39.5m and 40.5m respectively. According to Olayinka, (1992), areas of high thickness with low resistivity values of the weathered and fracture zones have been successfully identified as potential targets for siting boreholes. Abdullahi and Udensi, (2008), observed that an area with thick aquifer units of 15m and above may be generally appears good enough for drilling productive boreholes depend on the underlain materials such electrical resistivity, sand to clay ratio and the degree of saturation. Base on this information, the observed low resistivity zones range from $35\Omega\text{m}$ - $110\Omega\text{m}$ with average aquifer thickness of 30m (depicted by blue colour) in both Fig. 4.12 and 4.13, have been successfully identified as high aquifer potential zone targets for siting boreholes but may be poor site for heavy structures. The areas noted with relatively high resistivity and thick weathered layer range from $111\Omega\text{m}$ - $150\Omega\text{m}$ and 15-19m respectively (depicted by green colour) has also identified as good water bearing unit. The lower aquifer thickness region (depicted by yellow colour) found to be region around VES points $L_{1/4}$, $L_{2/4}$, $L_{3/5}$, and $L_{4/5}$, with thickness of 12.6m, 11.9m, 11.6m and 11.2m respectively. These regions could be considered as regions of average aquifer potential zones and it may be

relatively vulnerable to the near surface contamination due to its relative shallow nature. Considering the aquifer thickness and resistivity values (11m - 41m and 35 Ω m - 195 Ω m respectively), the study area appears good enough for siting of boreholes. In summary, the blue, green and red colour signified high, relatively high and moderate aquifer potential zones.

On the other hand, Fig4.14 and 4.15 show the orthographic projection map of aquifer thickness and the topography of the aquifer basement resistivity which correspond to fig 4.12 and 4.13.

Fig. 4.12: The Isopach Map of Weathered Layer

Fig. 4.13: The Iso-resistivity Map of Weathered Basement Layer

Fig. 4.14: The Orthographic projection map of Aquifer thickness.

Fig. 4.15: The Orthographic projection map of Aquifer resistivity

4.4.3 The Basement Rock Resistivity/Depth to the Basement

Fig. 4.16 and 4.17 show the basement rock resistivity and depth of the basement rock. The map was produced by contouring the resistivity values and overburden thickness of the basement rocks to reveal the high competence, competence and fairly competence zones of the study area. According to Aweto, (2012), when the bedrock has relatively low resistivity ($<750\Omega\text{m}$), this could indicate fracturing and high aquifer potentials.

Aboh and Osazuwa, (2000) ; Abdullahi and Udensi, (2008), noted that the variation in resistivities indicate the nature, strength or competence and the degree of the weathering of the basement of the study area, since the resistivity of the basement is a function of their degree of weathering and hence its strength. Fadele, et al., (2012), observed that the higher the layer resistivity value, the higher the competence of a layer. Based on these information, the basement rock competent underlain in the study area has been described as low/fairly competent, competent and highly competent zones as depicted by yellow, green and red colours respectively. The map shows that the study area is underlain by unfractured basement rock mostly at shallow depth (Fig 4.16 and 4.17). The depth to the basement and basement resistivity vary from 16m to 52m and $1000\ \Omega\text{m}$ to $7500\ \Omega\text{m}$ respectively. The deepest part (range from 25m to 52m) is the region already suggested for groundwater exploitation in this work. The VES

stations $L_{2/4}$, and $L_{5/6}$ depicted by red colour are highly resistive ($>6000 \Omega m$). The rocks in these regions are believed to be fresh basement with highest competence; and is competent enough to support any massive engineering structures while the region depicted by green colour is believed to be competent with resistivity values vary from $2000-5000 \Omega m$. Aboh, (2002), observed that the basement rocks resistivity ($<2000 \Omega m$) are less competent probably because they are fractured, faulted or heavily weathered. The areas depicted by yellow colour as shown in Fig 4.16 agreed with Aboh, (2002), has been described as regions of low/fairly basement resistivity which could be considered for siting small civil engineering structures.

On the other hand, Fig. 4.18 and 4.19 showing the Orthographic projection map of depth to the basement and the resistivity of the basement rock respectively were prepared to reveal the geometry or topography of the basement rock to enable a general view of the variation in the overburden thickness. The orthographic projection map (Fig. 4.18) showing the depth to the basement rock was produced by contouring the reciprocal of overburden thickness of the study area to reveal the real variation in the depth to the basement. In other word, the depression regions indicate high depth while the projection regions reveal the shallow depth region. The observed deep basement in the Northern parts are best region noted for waste and sewage disposal (Abdullahi and Udensi, 2008)

Fig. 4.16: The Iso-resistivity Map of Basement Rock

Fig. 4.17: Depth to the Basement (Overburden Thickness) Map

Fig. 4.18: The Orthographic projection map of the depth to the Basement

Fig. 4.19: Orthographic projection map of the Basement Resistivity Layer

4.4.4 Overburden

Fig. 4.22 shows the overburden thickness of the study area; the map was produced by contouring all layers above the presumably fresh basement. It varies from 16m to 52m. The North and Southwest part is thickest with average value of 42m, some part of NW, SS and East are relatively thick with average value of 26m while the SW and some part east are relatively low with the average value of 18m. According to Aweto, (2012), the study area may be considered protected against contamination/pollutant such as waste and sewage due to its relatively high depth to the basement bed rock. Generally, areas with thick overburden and low percentage of clay in which inter-granular flow is dominant are known to have high groundwater potential particularly in basement complex terrain (Lukuman, et al., 2015).

Fig. 4.20: The Overburden Thickness orthographic map of the Study Area.

4.5 Evaluation of Competence

Engineering competence of the subsurface can be qualitatively evaluated from the layer resistivity. The higher the layer resistivity value, the higher the competence of a layer (Fadele, et al., 2012). Based on the resistivity values of the different geoelectric layers and the various geologic units obtained, the study area has been classified into different competent zones (Fig. 4.16) namely; low/fairly competent, competent and high competent zone depicted yellow, green and red colour respectively. The competent and high competent zones are competent enough to support massive civil engineering structures. Fadele, et al., (2012), noted that the seasonal variation in the saturation of clay which causes ground movement could cause by clay swells and shrinkages; these factors could contribute to structural defect of building and. Considering the presence of consolidated laterite and quartzite veins in the study area beneath the clayey topsoil which extends beyond 2.5m could reduce the danger posed by clay formation to large buildings as well as tarred road. In summary, the interpreted data shows that there are no indications of any major trends such as fracture or faults that could aid building subsidence in the area identified as competent and highly competence zones. However, the areas ($< 2000\Omega m$) as depicted by yellow colour in Fig. 4.16 could indicate fractures or faults are low/fairly competent as noted by Aboh, (2002).

4.6 Evaluation of Aquifer Potential

Given the average resistivity and thicknesses values of the aquifer unit and the overburden thickness, (Fig. 4.5 – 4.9, 1.12 and 4.13), the study area is highly productive for groundwater exploitation. According to Ogundana and Talabi, (2014), the combination of overburden materials with the weathered/fractured basement constitutes aquiferous units within a study area although the sand and weathered/fractured basement units are largely responsible for the groundwater potential. Observed thickness and nature of the weathered layer are important parameters in the groundwater potential evaluation of a basement complex terrain, the layer is regarded as a significant water-bearing if significantly thick and the resistivity parameters suggest saturated conditions (Ogundana and Talabi, 2014). Shallow regions (<12m) may be vulnerable to contamination that may arise from human activities (Aweto, 2012). Areas with overburden thickness of 15m and above are good for groundwater development depend on the water bearing (aquifer) unit (Ogundana and Talabi, 2014). Base on this information, the study area can be considered largely productive zone for groundwater development in good quality and quantities; and may be less vulnerable to contamination that may arise from human activities due its relatively high depth in almost parts of the study area.

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A geophysical survey has been carried out with electrical resistivity method using Schlumberger electrode configuration to investigate the subsurface configuration of some parts of Kaduna Millennium City, Kaduna State. During the investigation, a total of thirty (30) VES points were established on five profiles in the direction of Northwest to Southeast (NW-SE) azimuth for all the profiles using Schlumberger vertical electrical soundings (VES). The interpretation revealed three to five subsurface layers with five-model curves H, KH, QH, HKH and QHA-types. KH and H-type curves were the dominant types with the values of H (26.7%), KH (26.7%), QH (23.3%), HKH (20%) and QHA (3.3%).

5.1 Conclusion

The interpretation of Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) data of the geophysical investigation of the study area has revealed three to five subsurface geoelectric layers and geologic sections, namely: topsoil/laterite/ quartzite/dry clay follow by wet clay/sand/silty, laterite/indurated laterite, and weathered basement and fractured/fresh basement rocks (Fig. 4.10 – 4.22). The weathered basement layer which is presumably clay/silt/sand constituted the aquifer units in the study area. The high thick weathered basement with a relatively low resistivity that covers almost the whole study area has been successfully identified as

potential aquifer zone targets for groundwater exploitation and it is large enough to harbour substantial quantity of water demand that may be arising in Kaduna Millennium City in future. However, the Southeast part (at VES stations $L_{2/4}$, $L_{3/5}$, $L_{4/4}$ and $L_{5/6}$) may be vulnerable to contamination that may arise from human activities such as indiscriminate disposal of wastes and surface runoff due to the relative shallow nature of the aquifer in these regions. The drainage pattern in the study area corresponds with the basement topography (towards the depressed area) this result in the effective recharge of the aquifer in the areas recommended in this study.

Similarly, the recommended competent zones for foundation design, engineering structural and other related works, are the regions where the basement materials are highly resistive with shallow depth, therefore are probably good zones for siting construction works. This study has been successfully described as low/fairly competent, competent and high competent zones base on the interpreted data. The area with high basement resistivity ($>6000\Omega\text{m}$) is underlain by high competent materials, and the area with relatively high resistivity ($>2000\Omega\text{m}$) as fairly competent zone. These regions of fairly and high competent zones are competent enough to support massive civil engineering structures; however, the superficial cover is loose and humus and fadama loam in some part of southeast of the study area; thus need to be totally excavated in any future structural and engineering works. The high topsoil resistivity in southeast and some part of north may not be unconnected with presence of surface outcrops and indurated laterite in the first layer which may also be of great importance as it reduces surface run off and aids infiltration into the underlying aquifer. The dc-resistivity method has proved very successful in

identification and delineation of interfacial configuration within the crystalline basement rocks.

5.2 Recommendations

Considering the magnitude of human loss associated with frequent building collapse and other disasters; it is necessary to investigate the geophysical properties of a site before any construction work. In the study area, there was no record or evidence of any geophysical investigation in the study area in the past. As a result of this, conclusion derived cannot be compared with any previous results. It is recommended therefore; that further geophysical investigations employing other methods should be carried out so as to validate this result and have detailed information about the subsurface in the study area.

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